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D8.1 First Interim report on Transnational Access 1

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Abbreviations

WP	Work Package
LL	Living Lab
JRAs	Joint Research Activities
TA	Transnational Access
CA	Contract Agreement
BA	Bilateral Agreement

Executive summary

This document aims to present an overview of the Transnational Access (TA) activities conducted in Work Package 8 (WP8) TA1 - TA to Living Lab infrastructures for rehabilitation as part of the VITALISE project. This first interim report encompasses six (6) research infrastructures that participated in the context of this work package, presenting information for both completed TA activities and also for the upcoming TA activities scheduled for the project's final phase.

In particular, the report includes comprehensive information for each of the participating research infrastructures. For completed TA activities, it provides a summary of every research project, the activities performed, the outcomes achieved, and any notable findings or advancements made. In addition, the report for the completed TA activities includes also some information regarding the effort and hours spent from the several professionals of the LL personnel for supporting the execution of each TA activity, both in person and remotely, as well as a summary of the researchers' TA evaluation and potential opportunities for future collaboration and common publications. This information showcases the value and impact of the TA program on the overall project objectives.

Additionally, the document outlines the upcoming TA activities that are going to be carried out during the project's final phase. It includes details such as the planned research objectives, anticipated benefits, and expected outcomes. These planned TA activities represent the project's ongoing commitment to exploring new avenues of research and maximizing the potential of Living Lab infrastructures.

As it is the first interim report, this document offers a snapshot of the collaborative efforts and achievements within WP8's TA1. It signifies the project's progress towards fostering innovation, knowledge exchange, and interdisciplinary research in the realm of rehabilitation. This report serves as a valuable resource for stakeholders, researchers, and policymakers, providing insights into the project's TA outcomes and setting the stage for the comprehensive final report due in Month 36.

1 Introduction

1.1 Description of WP8

WP8 deals with the centralised and coordinated design and implementation of transnational access for infrastructures related to the rehabilitation domain in VITALISE. Under transnational access we refer to the usage of VITALISE infrastructures by users located in other countries than the location of the respective accessed infrastructure. This WP information is linked to the activities and information collected in WP9 and WP10.

VITALISE infrastructures are fully open to all users that have a clear and significant research objective. For each infrastructure there is an estimated access of 30 days for each project that can be performed either physically or remotely.

The research infrastructures participating in WP8 are the following ones:

- AUTH, Centrifuge rehabilitation Living Lab (M18-M36) led by AUTH
- THOMAS MORE Motion Lab, Mobilab & Care (M18-M36) led by LiCaLab
- GAIA, Ocean Living Lab for rehabilitation (M18-M36) led by GAIA
- INTRAS, rehabilitation Living Lab (M18-M36) led by INTRAS
- LAUREA Simulated Hospital (M18-M36) led by LAUREA
- McGill, CRIR Rehabilitation Living Lab (M18-M36) led by McGill

1.2 Purpose of the document

This document aims to present all the data collection and analysis that has been done between M18-M24 of the VITALISE project regarding the Transnational Access (TA) to research infrastructures. The final version of the report is going to be released by the end of the project on M36 (March 2024). This document not only includes the performed TA activities but also the planned ones for the next period of the project. The report is linked to the activities and information collected in the Transactional Accesses of WP8 and WP9, having the same structure as D10.1 "First Interim Report on Transnational Access 3" and D9.1 "First Interim Report on Transnational Access 2".

1.3 Document Structure

The deliverable is structured as such:

- **Section 1 (Introduction)** provides a description of Work Package 8 (WP8), outlines the purpose of the document, and presents the structure of the report.
- **Section 2 (Finalized Transnational Access Projects)** provides details for each Transnational Access (TA) project, evaluation from researchers, and some information about the number of hours spent by the Living Lab personnel.
- **Section 3 (Planning of Upcoming TA Projects)** offers updates on overall planning. For each Living Lab infrastructure, it presents data for each planned TA, such as the project name, planned TA period, Consortium Agreement (CA) signed and uploaded by the applicants, CA signed by the European Network of Living Labs (ENoLL), CA sent and signed by the applicants, signing of the Bilateral Agreement (BA, if applicable), initial questionnaires, and visits performed.
- **Section 4 (Conclusion)** provides some concluding remarks on this deliverable.

2 Finalized Transnational Access projects.

This section presents one by one the TA projects that have been performed in each of the WP9 Living Lab infrastructures so far.

2.1 AUTH Centrifuge rehabilitation Living Lab

At this point, none of the projects addressed to the “AUTH Human Centrifuge and Rehabilitation Living Lab” have been started or completed. Nevertheless, two projects have been accepted for implementation. The first project is the realization of an oddball EEG paradigm in different G-levels, and the protocol to be followed has been co-designed between the applicants and the AUTH team.. The second project has just passed the feasibility evaluation phase, no official communication has been launched at this time and will thus be included in the next TA report. More detailed information are included in the next section that summarizes that planning of the upcoming activities.

2.2 THOMAS MORE Motion Lab - Mobilab & Care

None of the TA projects using the THOMAS MORE Motion lab infrastructure is completed at this point. One study has started with a first period of data collection in May 2023, but a second follow-up visit is expected to take place during the end of August or beginning of September (ID 43). The second project is planned for October 23 - February 2024 (ID 57). More information regarding these studies is included in the next section.

2.3 GAIA- Ocean Living Lab for rehabilitation

Not started yet. Expected for the period September-December 2023.

The information regarding upcoming TA is included in the next section.

2.4 INTRAS rehabilitation Living Lab

None of the TA projects using the INTRAS Rehabilitation Living Lab infrastructure has started at this point. A first study dedicated to the Exploration of natural language processing techniques for non-invasive monitoring of mental disorders in elderly people from home has just been accepted and is expected for August-September 2023 (ID98). The second project is planned for September-October 2023 (ID92) focused in Enhancing Usability, Efficiency, and Satisfaction in ICT Utilization for Older Adults. More details will be included in the next TA report. More information regarding these studies is included in the next section.

2.5 LAUREA- Laurea Simulated Hospital

2.5.1 Matias Ignacio De La Calle. ALMA MATER STUDIORUM UNIVERSITY OF BOLOGNA

The TA researcher conducted 28 semi-structured interviews among various Laurea Living Lab experts who have been executing Living Lab projects in various thematic areas and/or were acting as lecturers e.g. in a Service design master program. Furthermore, he was also doing direct participant observation during the lectures as well as participating in a “Robota Project” session where experts and end users with mental and physical impairment were interacting.

2.6 McGill- CRIR Rehabilitation Living Lab

We currently have one TA project using the McGill-CRIR Rehabilitation Living Lab infrastructure. The TA researchers’ visit (Vingron & Müller Karoza (ID22 and ID44) began in July 2023 and will last 4 weeks. The aim of this project is to characterize the effects of listening to audioguides while viewing works of art on engagement, information processing and well-being with the overall goal of increasing engagement with the works of art. A second TA project is planned for August-September 2023 (Elisabeth Steindl, ID29). This project aims to shed light on privacy and data protection challenges that are specific to the deployment of IoT devices for mental health. A third TA project is also planned for August 2023 (K Kostopoulou, ID48).

Two more TA projects will be launched later in the Fall of 2023: 1) Miklos Kozlovszky (ID14) will undertake a project that will focus on the efficient processing and analysis of measured physiological (cardiovascular and postural/movement) parameters using IT tools and 2) Christina Manouilidou and Georgia Roumpea (ID25) will carry out a project to explore the effect of physical activity, in the form of structured exercise, on rehabilitation outcomes including language processing of people with aphasia and healthy controls. More details on these upcoming projects are included in the next section.

2.6.1 Naomi Vingron (lead researcher) and Lea Müller Karoza. Goethe University, Germany. Title: A Day at the Museum: Using Audio-Guided Visual Search to Increase Engagement Among Older Adults Visiting Art Museums.

This project will be conducted in two phases: phase one will constitute a proof of principle study, using a visual search task carried out by young adults in a laboratory at Goethe University in Frankfurt, Germany and at Concordia University in Montreal, Canada. Participants will be viewing a total of 12 paintings (selected from the Städel Museum Frankfurt and the Montreal Museum of Fine Arts) while listening to audio guides. Importantly, six of the paintings will be viewed while listening to the original audio guides that the museum is currently using while the remaining six paintings will be viewed while listening to an audio guide that includes embedded search tasks. In both conditions participants' eye movements are recorded while they view the paintings using an eye tracker set up on a desk (Eyelink 1000, SR Research). The goals of this phase are to (a) compare visual scanning patterns when participants are listening to a conventional audio guide or one that is explicitly developed to guide visual attention and (b) establish the reliability of the link between auditorily presented instructions, eye movements and subsequent recall. Phase two of the experiment will be conducted across two museums, namely the Städel Museum Frankfurt and the Montreal Museum of Fine Arts. Both museums specialize in modern art and include vast collections of paintings, sculptures and other artifacts. Here, older adults will be asked to view the original paintings while listening to our audio guides and having their eye movements recorded using portable Pupil Labs eyetracking glasses. The goal of this phase is to further establish the link described above, as well as investigate whether the employment of these guided search tasks is associated with an improved museum experience among older adults.

3 Planning of upcoming TA projects

Due to the fact that this document is an interim report and not all the TAs have been finalized yet, this section provides an overview and a short description of the upcoming TA projects that will be performed in the WP9 Living Lab infrastructures.

3.1 Overall planning updates

The following infographic offers information regarding the status of the TA for WP8. The infographic includes aggregated information from the three (3) VITALISE Open calls, taking into account both completed and upcoming projects.

Figure 1: VITALISE TA WP8

Number of applicants:31

From this number 61,3% are female, 32,3% male and the rest of applicants N/A.

Regarding the domain of applicants, the main domain is Academia accounting for 75 % of the applicants followed by the industrial applicants with 12,5% and the entrepreneur's domain with 6,3% of the applicants.

Regarding the working countries, the majority of the applications came from European countries.

3.2 AUTH Centrifuge rehabilitation Living Lab

Table 1: Current status of each upcoming TA project in AUTH centrifuge rehabilitation Living Lab

Project name	TA planned period	CA signed by the applicants and uploaded	CA signed by ENoLL	CA sent signed to the applicants	Sign the BA (optional)	Initial questionnaires	Visit performed
n23	July-August & November-	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	No	No

	December 2023						
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ID23 Understanding neuromuscular adaptations in increased gravity with the short-arm human centrifuge

This project is going to be launched in autumn 2023. Its main focus will be the assessment of the oddball paradigm in healthy adults. The study aims to examine potential differences induced in the cognitive processing of adults due to different gravity levels. Furthermore, the applicants aim to examine differences in cognitive responses across the lifespan.

As a result, healthy volunteers will be recruited, belonging to different age groups. Young adults and older adults. The specific inclusion and exclusion criteria have not been defined yet. All participants will undergo a single centrifugation protocol at different G-levels. The oddball paradigm will be measured in all these levels.

The external researchers will use their own EEG equipment. In order to test equipment compatibility, the main researcher Uros Marusic will visit the premises of the living lab for a few days between July 24th and August 4th. Then, a team of 4 will come to the infrastructure to carry out the pilots between November 13th and December 8th.

3.3 THOMAS MORE Motion Lab - Mobilab & Care

This section presents a summary and the overall status of LiCalab’s upcoming TA projects.

Table 2: Current status of each upcoming TA project in Thomas More Motion Lab- Mobilab & Care

Project name	TA planned period	CA signed by the applicants and uploaded	CA signed by ENoLL	CA sent signed to the applicants	Sign the BA (optional)	Initial questionnaires	Visit performed
ID 43	MAY 23 AUG-SEP 23	YES	YES	YES	NO	YES	PARTLY
ID 57	OCT23-FEB24	NO	NO	NO	NO	YES	NO

Note. ID 57 combines the use of the THOMAS MORE Motion lab infrastructure with the LiCalab older adults’ homes.

ID 43 Dynawork: Smart uniform testing, Sabri Mahdaoui, Assen Tchorbadjieff, Bulgaria.

Ergonomics is the science of fitting workplace conditions and job demands to the capability of the working population. The goal of ergonomics is to reduce stress and eliminate injuries and disorders associated with the overuse of muscles, bad posture, and repeated tasks. A workplace ergonomics program can aim to prevent or control injuries and illnesses by eliminating or reducing worker exposure to risk factors using engineering and administrative controls. Risk factors include awkward postures, repetition, material handling, force, mechanical compression, vibration, temperature extremes, glare, inadequate lighting, and duration of exposure.

Ergonomic Assessments are mostly carried out manually by an expert, but it seems that this old-fashioned approach gives poor results, consumes time, covers just some small period of the working activity of the operator and angles are estimated on a feeling.

Dynaback’s objective is to make the process simple and automated. Dynaback is a uniform with integrated sensors in textile for motion capture, that can be worn on the work floor.

Expected outcome:

In this study, Sabri and Assen will compare the results of the Dynaback shirt with the results of validated measuring equipment from the Thomas More Motion lab (TEA CAPTIV T-Sens Motion (IMU)). Human movement data while performing professional tasks will be collected simultaneously using the Dynaback suit and the validated IMU sensors. The data will be translated into a set of parameters, which can be linked to risk and as for example described in existing, RULA, OCRA index, RULA, KIM manual actions, HARM, strain index. Analyses of the risky movements are performed per joint.

ID 57 Physical activity levels and physical function in mid-life women, Oonagh Giggins (Lead applicant), Suzanne Smith, Dundalk Institute of Technology, Dublin Road, Dundalk, Co Louth, Ireland.

This research seeks to address the issue of physical inactivity and functional decline in mid-life-menopausal women. Physical inactivity is a global health issue, with one in four adults not meeting the recommended target levels for physical activity. Physical activity is reported to decline with advancing age, and middle-aged women are more vulnerable to become physically inactive with the menopausal transition. Regular physical activity results in many health benefits and is an important determinant of physical performance.

Poor physical performance is a predictor of frailty, disability and loss of independence and the menopause transition has been shown to be associated with decreased functioning.

The aim of this TA is to examine physical activity levels and physical function in mid-life women and examine whether the menopause is associated with an accelerated decline in physical function and physical activity levels and increased musculoskeletal issues.

To achieve the aim of this research, the following **objectives** have been identified:

- To undertake an examination of physical capability among mid-life (peri-menopausal, menopausal, or post-menopausal) women.
- To capture a quantitative physical capability dataset in this cohort using body worn sensors and compare sensor measurements with measurements obtained using traditional means.
- To characterise daily physical activity levels in the same cohort over a 3-month period.
- To examine differences in physical capability, physical activity and musculoskeletal issues across menopausal stages

This research will firstly involve a cross-sectional study and then a subsequent longitudinal study, to determine the physical activity levels and physical capability of a cohort of mid-life women who are also experiencing musculoskeletal problems.

Data collection:

- **Demographics**
- **Physical health:** heart rate at rest, blood pressure, weight, body mass index and percentage body fat. Self-reported past medical history (including obstetric and gynaecologic history), use of medications, presence of musculoskeletal disease or conditions, lifestyle related factors (smoking habits, alcohol consumption and daily physical activity levels).
- **Quality of life:** Menopause Rating Scale (MRS)
- **Pain:** the McGill Pain Questionnaire (MPQ)
- **Menopause status** (WHO classifications)
- **Physical capability tests:** Timed Up & Go Test (TUG), the 6-minute walk test (6MWT), postural stability tests, gait speed tests, and grip strength test.
- **Physical activity:** Withings smart watch: Daily physical activity levels (step count) and sleep

3.4 GAIA- Ocean Living Lab for rehabilitation

Table 3: Current status of each upcoming TA project in GAIA Ocean Living Lab for rehabilitation

Project name	TA planned period	CA signed by the applicants and uploaded	CA signed by ENoLL	CA sent signed to the applicants	Sign the BA (optional)	Initial questionnaires	Visit performed
ID69	SEP-DEC	NO	NO	NO	NO	NO	NO
ID84	SEP-DEC	NO	NO	NO	NO	NO	NO
ID97	SEP-DEC	NO	NO	NO	NO	NO	NO

ID69. Alon Meiri (lead applicant), Bar Yitzhaki- Ozean living lab.

Public entities are nowadays trying to adapt public spaces to new uses addressed to new sociological needs. Ozean Living Lab is working in close collaboration with Gernika-Lumo municipality, with the participation of entities that work closely with civil society such as the City Council itself and Gernika Gogoratz, a Research Centre for Peace created by decision of the Basque Parliament in April 1987, coinciding with the 50th anniversary of the bombing of Gernika.

Our objective is to generate a Performing Arts-Smart space for dialogue, citizen-centred, generating an open innovation ecosystem based on an inclusive user co-creation approach, integrating research and innovation processes in a real-life community and setting.

The materials to be used are:

- Smart watches and elastic smart bands for the users
- Digital cameras for the recording.

Data to be collected:

There are a multitude of different things that could be measured to gauge the success of a performing arts in Smart spaces for wellbeing programme and there is a tradeoff between obtaining useful metrics and the burden it places on participants. As a general principle, any measurements that are made should employ tests that are suitable for use in an older adult population, and tests that are externally validated. Employing measurements that can be conducted in field-based settings is also important.

Data to be collected: Quality of life e.g. AQoL, Symptoms (fatigue e.g.FSS); Distress (anxiety e.g. GAD7); Self-reported health status (e.g. SF-36); Warwick well-being scale; WHOQOL. And also biometric data like heart rate, cardiorespiratory endurance, muscle strength and endurance, balance, agility, speed, flexibility and body composition.

ID84. Ananya Tiwari- Ozean living lab

This research study will be based in the GAIA OZEAN living lab, located in the UNESCO-designated Urdaibai Biosphere Reserve in Basque, Spain. This study will analyze the role of ecosystem-based climate adaptation strategies in reducing local coastal climate risks (such as erosion, coastal flooding, extreme weather events, sea level rise etc). Urdaibai Biosphere Reserve is a region filled with biodiversity, and home to 45,000 inhabitants, 80% of which are concentrated in the towns of Gernika and Bermeo.

The marshlands are critical for bird life, both as a nesting area and as a stopping or wintering site. The coastal wetlands are also a natural nursery of great importance for many marine species that spend their first years in this area. Besides its environmental wonders, Urdaibai features a cultural,

architectural and archaeological heritage that is of high symbolic importance to the Basque people, such as Katillotxu and the Roman settlement of Forua. Gernika, made famous by the infamous bombing and Pablo Picasso's painting, is also located in the area.

Around 14% of the population makes a living out of the primary sector, mainly in farming, cattle-raising, forestry and fishing. The main expected impacts of climate change on this region include increased flooding and sea-level rise, reduction in annual precipitation, increased temperatures, and more. This will impact sectors like agriculture and forestry, as well as marine biodiversity.

The Climate Change Strategy of the Basque Country to 2050 states that the climate scenarios for Basque have broad horizons, specifically when it comes to climate adaptation. They present a level of uncertainty that can reduce gradually through more research. The report also highlights the need to generate local knowledge in Basque Country, by guiding lines of research in this regard, so that results can be obtained to facilitate decision-making. It also emphasises the need to mainstream climate action, to make communities less vulnerable to climate change, and the necessity of climate policy to bring all stakeholders of society onboard. It suggests institutional and stakeholder collaboration as necessities to address the cross-cutting nature of climate change. Finally, it states that effective climate adaptation strategies can also have co-benefits for socioeconomic well-being.

The GAIA OZEAN living lab provides a suitable platform to address all of these interconnected issues. The quadruple helix model, part of the living lab structure, provides a platform for effective stakeholder engagement from different sections of society, including academia, public sector, industry and civil society. The infrastructure and research capacity available in the living lab can facilitate a study to analyse the current climate adaptation strategies as well as plan future ecosystem-based adaptation approaches in Urdaibai, Basque.

Since this living lab focuses on ecosystem services, biodiversity, green economy, and societal well-being, this study will explicitly analyse the role of ecosystem services in supporting climate adaptation goals, as well as providing socioeconomic co-benefits to enhance overall community wellbeing.

The OZEAN living lab focuses on citizen-driven innovation for the ocean. This study will involve citizen and stakeholder engagement, to analyse the most effective coastal adaptation strategies in Basque to ensure community wellbeing, based in the living lab principles of co-creation and co-design.

This research will use the knowledge generated within the ongoing EU Horizon 2020 SCORE project, and design a study to compare the ecosystem-based climate adaptation strategies in the SCORE Sligo Coastal City Living Lab and the VITALISE GAIA OZEAN living lab, thus encouraging knowledge-exchange and collaboration between the two EU projects.

ID97 Katalin Kovacs (lead applicant), Istvan Karsa – Ozean living lab

The aim of the project is to analyse the effect of movement analysis, using smart tools and personal feedback, on the motivation level of senior citizens for physical activity.

Nowadays, digital technology provides a broad repertoire of movement analysis tools that are easy for participants to reach data.

By using smart devices, all users can monitor their physical activity indicators, both in terms of mechanical and physiological aspects. It is common theory, that with smart devices, there is no need of specialists, because the devices also provide an immediate assessment of energy consumption, distance traveled, average and maximum speed and step count, as well as heart rate values that characterize the work of the heart, both in terms of time series data and load zones. There are other options for assessing the stress level, sleep quality, and in some cases the level of fitness. Tools are also available that enable further evaluation of the mechanical characteristics of the movement, where the movement coordination of the individual limbs can also be monitored, enabling possible muscular balance problems and unjustified fatigue factors to be filtered out.

The long-term goal of the research is to create movement guidelines for the elderly, where quality execution is emphasized, increasing effective implementation so that participants are motivated to exercise and remain physically active.

3.5 INTRAS rehabilitation Living Lab

Table 4: Current status status of each upcoming TA project in INTRAS rehabilitation Living Lab

Project name	TA planned period	CA signed by the applicants and uploaded	CA signed by ENoLL	CA sent signed to the applicants	Sign the BA (optional)	Initial questionnaires	Visit performed
ID92/5	NOV-DEC	NO	NO	NO	NO	NO	NO
ID98/1	AUG-SEP	NO	NO	NO	NO	NO	NO

ID 92 EDAD.TECH Welfare Testing - Enhancing Usability, Efficiency, and Satisfaction in ICT Utilization for Older Adults

Researchers: Lorena Paz, Universidad de Flores, Argentina (Lead Applicant), Jesica Cuellar, Samantha Gavilan, Daniela Tamashiro, Agustin Aramburu

Study: The EDAD.TECH action research project aims to understand the emotional dimension of older adults' relationship with information and communication technologies (ICT). The project has identified ergonomic issues and design violations in various technological tools, which often deter seniors from their use due to fear and suspicion.

The project has been successful in achieving emotional empowerment through its teaching processes, enabling older adults to use and engage with ICT more meaningfully. To further improve these efforts, the project is looking to explore developments related to well-being, emotion, and behavior regulation, potentially leveraging multisensory stimulation and mindfulness techniques.

Key project objectives include testing innovative technologies for emotional well-being at the INTRAS Foundation and assessing the SERENHE prototype (a telerehabilitation platform with virtual reality technologies). It also aims to gather user insights through participatory methods to guide the development of new features, such as guided breathing exercises.

The project's methodology follows a Design Thinking approach and uses a mixed methodological approach with both qualitative and quantitative data. The team comprises experts in various fields such as behavioral psychology, interaction design, software design, accessibility, and usability testing.

The project will unfold in several phases, including exploration, testing, co-creation, and reporting. During these stages, the team will conduct heuristic analysis, usability testing following ISO 25000 standards, and co-creation sessions with real users. They will finally generate a report of the testing and co-creation experience and provide improvement suggestions.

The project's anticipated impact is to improve the usability, efficiency, effectiveness, and satisfaction of ICT use for older adults, fostering their emotional well-being. Through universal design guidelines, accessibility guidelines, and usability criteria, it aims to contribute to the development of a true care economy. It also seeks to enhance interoperability in system development while maintaining ethical and quality standards in the design of technologies for human development.

ID98 NLPElderly - Exploration of natural language processing techniques for non-invasive monitoring of mental disorders in elderly people from home

Researchers: Andrea Johana Chaves, Trascender Global S.A.S., Colombia

Study: This Transnational Access Project, titled "Exploration of natural language processing techniques for non-invasive monitoring of mental disorders in elderly people from home" (NLPElderly), aims to address the challenge of mental health issues in the aging population. The project proposes the use of Natural Language Processing (NLP) methods to analyze unstructured data and identify patterns of mental disorders among elderly individuals.

The project is structured around three main objectives. The first objective is to identify and adapt an appropriate dataset that provides information on mental disorders in elderly individuals. The second objective is to train and fine-tune transformer-based models to determine patterns of mental disorders. The third objective is to validate the performance of these models using different evaluation metrics.

The execution of the project will take place in three phases:

- **Dataset Definition:** The team will define a data collection method and also explore open-source databases to identify patterns of mental disorders.
- **NLP Methods Application:** The project will apply transfer learning methodologies based on transformer models to perform NLP tasks. This phase will mainly focus on sentiment analysis and knowledge extraction using named entity recognition.
- **Model Performance Evaluation:** The model's performance will be evaluated using metrics such as precision, recall, F-score, and accuracy.

The project anticipates challenges such as potential difficulties in obtaining relevant data and computational limitations of the utilized resources. Strategies have been outlined to mitigate these risks.

The impact of the project is expected to be significant. The application of NLP techniques on text data can help extract valuable insights and discover new possible patterns of mental disorders in elderly people. This will not only aid in diagnosing diseases and identifying patient risk factors early but also support clinical research and evidence-based medicine. Furthermore, it can also serve as a step towards automation and telediagnosics in mental health care.

3.6 LAUREA- Laurea Simulated Hospital

Table 5: Current status of each upcoming TA project in LAUREA- Laurea Simulated Hospital

Project name	TA planned period	CA signed by the applicants and uploaded	CA signed by ENoLL	CA sent signed to the applicants	Sign the BA (optional)	Initial questionnaires	Visit performed
ID51	NOV	NO	NO	YES	NO	NO	NO

ID51 Roisin MOLLOY, Mandy WRIGHT, from TriMedika Ltd, UK. Project: TRIMEDIKA - Evaluation of TRITEMP connected thermometer within the nursing workflow within hospital

“Evaluation of TRITEMP connected thermometer within the nursing workflow within hospital” project aims to gather user experience feedback and improvement suggestions from nursing staff (usability, advantages/disadvantages) and patients (comfort of use, advantages/disadvantages) regarding TRITEMP thermometer. Furthermore, study also evaluates the impact of using a connected vs. non-contact thermometer on cost, time and delivery of care, and potentially demonstrate the possible 10x improvement. The study involves ‘operators’ (i.e. nurses), each taking temperature readings from at least 10 different subjects to evaluate the use of the TRITEMP connected device within the usual nursing workflow. The ‘subjects’ may not be necessarily real-life patients. A surgical ward focusing on joint replacement surgery from Helsinki University Hospital is agreed to participate to

the study and Laurea's nursing education have confirmed that testing among nursing students could be integrated in their clinical workshop teaching. The residential care home (Lauttasaaren senioritalo) have also confirmed 20-30 potential test users (nurses). Ethical application will be sent to Human Sciences Ethics Committee and Research Nurse Director in university hospital ethics committee on 5th of September. Research visit is planned for November. Contract agreements are expected to be signed on August by latest.

3.7 McGill- CRIR Rehabilitation Living Lab

Table 6: Current status of each upcoming TA project in GAIA Ocean Living Lab for rehabilitation

Project name	TA planned period	CA signed by the applicants and uploaded	CA signed by ENoLL	CA sent signed to the applicants	Sign the BA (optional)	Initial questionnaires	Visit performed
ID29	AUG-SEPT 2023	yes	yes	yes	no	no	no
ID48	FALL 2023	no	no	no	no	no	no
ID14	FALL 2023	yes	yes	yes	no	no	no
ID25	FALL 2023	no	no	no	no	no	no

ID29. Elisabeth Steindl, University of Vienna, Austria.

Title: Privacy and Data Protection Challenges Affecting Internet of Things for Mental Health: Comparative Perspectives and Pathways for Soft Regulation in Europe and Canada (IoT-MH)

In an attempt to contribute to ongoing policy initiatives and discussions on the regulation of e-mental health services, the project aims to shed light on privacy and data protection challenges that are specific to the deployment of IoT devices for mental health. By collaborating with two Living Labs (the AUTH Living Environment Simulation and the McGill-UdeM-CRIR Living Lab), the project's aim is to provide a comparative account of regulatory deficiencies and assess whether soft law instruments could facilitate good practices in the EU and Canada.

In order to make the most of this potential research collaboration, the project is being conducted onsite in two Living Labs of the VITALISE Project (AUTH Living Environment Simulation and the McGill-UdeM-CRIR Living Lab) in the course of a 30 day research stay (Expected August-September 2023). During this period, one of the researchers (Richard Rak) will access the AUTH Living Environment Simulation, while Elisabeth Steindl will be at the McGill-UdeM-CRIR Living Lab. Their combined endeavors will gather insights into what specific privacy and data protection-related concerns (e.g. legal uncertainties, security risks, data management issues) have emerged in the development and testing of IoT devices for mental health in two different regulatory and research environments.

ID14. Miklos Kozlovsky, Óbuda University, Hungary. Title: Testing state-of-the-art wearable health sensors and their data analysis methods

This project focuses on the efficient processing and analysis of measured physiological (cardiovascular and postural/movement) parameters using IT tools. The planned research strongly builds on the use of high-performance infrastructures with high computing capacity to solve the following problems:

1. Adapting and further extend the theoretical background of the previous, formal definition of the remote patient monitoring with continuous, cardiovascular and posture monitoring using wearable measuring devices.

2. Effective analysis of complex data streams (e.g.: continuous ECG, or continuous movement data) from continuous parameter monitoring. Analyzing the collected data is a very difficult task. Evaluating individual, multi-channel, minute-time measurements has been solved for years. However, automated processing of continuous, long-lasting, long-term ECG measurements (up to months of measurements) is still unresolved. The same is valid for movement and posture data.

3. The accuracy of the evaluation of remote ECG measurements and posture data (mainly due to the unknown measurement environment) is still significantly lower than expected by the medical professionals.

The research will focus primarily on the analysis of cardiovascular data and movement/posture data as a data structure and on the algorithmic methods for data evaluation and their applicability. The project will be conducted onsite at the McGill-UdeM-CRIR Living Lab in the Fall 2023.

ID25: Christina Manouilidou (lead researcher) and Georgia Roumpea, University of Ljubljana, Slovenia. Title: Ready, steady, go: the effect of PHysical Exerise on LAngeuage performance post-stroke and in healthy aging (PHELA)

The primary objective of the study is to explore the effect of physical activity, in the form of structured exercise, on rehabilitation outcomes and more specifically on language processing of people with aphasia and healthy controls. While the benefits of exercise on various cognitive functions are already known, little is known about the effect of exercise on language performance. In addition, the effect of physical activity as a means of improving language performance in stroke-induced aphasia has not been investigated in depth. The study will further investigate the effect of language in stroke and in healthy aging. Furthermore, the researchers aim to broaden the scope of language domains under investigation by including areas of language performance not previously looked at including more complex language processes, pertaining to complex syntax and complex word structure.

For the assessment of linguistic performance of areas under investigation two short language tasks will be performed prior to intervention program and immediately after: 1. Single word Naming task: participants will be shown pictures and they will be asked to name the objects, activities and agents depicted in them. This task will test their anomia levels. 2. Sentence-picture matching task: participants will hear/read a complex sentence and they'll have to choose the picture that best describes it. This task will test their sentence comprehension levels.

After completion of the baseline measurements, the participants will be enrolled in 4-week intervention. The sessions will be carried out 1-2 times a week in actual gym conditions while the control group will receive an educational workshop on the importance of physical activity for health

but will not participate in active sessions during the 4-week course. The intervention program will include light-to-moderate intensity resistance exercise, cardiovascular exercise and stretching. The intensity of the exercise will be tracked by heart rate monitors and self-reported perceived exertion. The intensity of the conventional exercise will be varied across participants and across the single sessions. All measurements will be performed in the premises of the McGill-UdeM-CRIR Living Lab in the Fall of 2023.

4 Conclusion

This document presents an overview about the performed and upcoming TA activities to six research infrastructures that participate in this work package, highlighting the significance of transnational access in facilitating collaborative research efforts across different research infrastructures. By granting researchers access to state-of-the-art Living Lab infrastructures, the project aims to foster innovation, advance knowledge in the field of transitional care and highlight its critical role.

As the first interim report, this document offers a snapshot of the collaborative efforts and achievements within WP8's TA1. It signifies the project's progress towards fostering innovation, knowledge exchange, and interdisciplinary research in the realm of transitional care. This report serves as a valuable resource for stakeholders, researchers, and policymakers, providing insights into the project's TA outcomes and setting the stage for the comprehensive final report due in month 36 (March 2024).